

MICROSTRUCTURE EVOLUTION DURING SOLIDIFICATION OF SiC_p REINFORCED Al - ALLOY METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Al-4Cu-1vol% SiC_p and Al-4Cu-1Mg-1vol% SiC_p composites were processed by the melt-stir casting technique and unidirectionally solidified in refractory molds having copper chills at the bottom and exothermic powder at the top. Freezing rates were varied in these castings by varying the chill thicknesses. The interaction between particle and secondary dendrite arm has been studied.

Al-3.2Cu and Al-3.2Cu-5vol% SiC_p composites were multidirectionally solidified using permanent molds. The experimentally measured interface velocity was compared with critical velocities (for entrapment/engulfment) based on various theoretical models. Due to particle-solidification front interaction, a marked change in morphology of the solid liquid interface and the solute diffusion field has been observed.

INTRODUCTION

Amongst several processes currently in usage for the production of particulate reinforced MMCs, solidification processing is proven to be attractive because of its simplicity, economy and flexibility. As pointed out by various workers and reviewed extensively by Mortensen and Jin [1], solidification behaviour of the matrix material is significantly influenced by the presence of the reinforcing ceramic particles in the melt-particle slurry. Changes in the solidification phenomenon due to the presence of dispersed ceramic reinforcements can be analyzed with respect to: a) Micro and macro segregation of the reinforcing phase in the solidified casting. b) Effect of particles on the morphology of the advancing solidification front. c) Interaction of the particle with the solute diffusion field ahead of an advancing solidification front.

When an advancing solid-liquid interface interacts with a foreign particle suspended in the melt, the particle can either be engulfed (i.e. engulfment of the particle by the growing solid) or entrapped (i.e. trapped in the interdendritic region in case of a dendritic solidification) or pushed (i.e. pushed in the growth direction ahead of the interface). Several workers have attempted to theoretically model the particle-solidification front interaction in one component system under unidirectional plane front solidification conditions. Theoretical models proposed, use different criteria to predict pushing or engulfment. While most of the theoretical models are based on velocity of growth front [2-5], Zubko *et al.* [6] and Surappa *et al.* [7] models are based on ratios of thermal conductivity and thermal diffusivity, respectively, of particle and melt. However, in most practical applications, alloys rather than pure metals are used and the solidification conditions generally encountered in most of the cast products are cellular, dendritic or eutectic. Sekhar and Trivedi [8] have observed changes in the shape of the advancing solid- liquid interface due to particle-solute field interaction and resultant change in particle engulfment mechanisms under different solidification conditions. Some workers have studied the particle-solidification front interactions during solidification of MMCs [9,10]. However, there is not much work on the role of reinforcement particles in governing the interface morphology during composite processing.

The purpose of the present work is to study the particle-solidification front interaction during dendritic solidification of Al alloys in the presence of SiC particulates. The influence of the particles on the morphology of the growing crystal has been studied. Particle-solute field interaction and solute segregation have also been studied during solidification of composites.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

The preheated SiC particles were dispersed in the Al-alloy melt by stir-casting technique and the composite slurry was superheated to (730°C) and poured into molds. In order to achieve unidirectional solidification, refractory molds with copper chills at the bottom were used. Molds were heated to 700°C before pouring and immediately after pouring, the melt was covered by exothermic powder on the top. The freezing rates in castings were varied using copper chills of different thicknesses. Each casting was identified by the ratio of its height to the thickness of the bottom chill (Hcast/Tchill).

Cylindrical castings of Al-3.2Cu alloy and Al-3.2Cu-5 vol% SiC_p composite were cast in cast iron molds and cooling rate was recorded by inserting thermocouples at various locations along the central axis.

TABLE 1. Details of castings prepared under different solidification conditions.

S.No.	System	SiC _p Average size (μm)	Hcast/Tchill	Casting designation
1.	Al-4Cu-1 vol% SiC _p	40 (μm)	4 *	AC4
2.	Al-4Cu-1 vol% SiC _p	40 (μm)	6 *	AC6
3.	Al-4Cu-1Mg-1vol% SiC _p	40 (μm)	2 *	ACM2
4.	Al-4Cu-1Mg-1vol% SiC _p	40 (μm)	5 *	ACM5
5.	Al-4Cu-1Mg-1vol% SiC _p	40 (μm)	6 *	ACM6
6.	Al-3.2Cu-5 vol% SiC _p	12 (μm)	#	ACI

* - Copper chill and exothermic powder (Unidirectional Solidification), # - Cast iron mold, AC - Al-Cu-SiC_p composite, ACM - Al-Cu-Mg-SiC_p composite and ACI - Al-Cu-SiC_p com-

The details of the castings are given in Table 1. All these castings were cut and polished along the meridian plane. Measurement of secondary dendrite arm spacing was made using line-intercept method and the volume fraction measurement was carried out by point counting technique. The Neophot optical microscope was used for this purpose. A 20 Kv Cambridge SEM with EDAX attachment was used to obtain information on solute distribution.

RESULTS

1. DISTRIBUTION OF SiC PARTICLES, MATRIX MICROSTRUCTURE AND CRITICAL VELOCITY

Figs. 1a and 1b show the typical macrostructures observed along the meridian plane in AC, and ACI castings. In case of AC, the particles have been pushed upwards unidirectionally from the chill end in the direction of growth of the solid, to the top region. Similar features were observed in case of ACM.

Figure 1. Macrostructures of (a) AC4, revealing particle pushing to the top and (b) ACI, indicating inverted 'V' type particle depleted zone.

The normalised distance of pushing (i.e. the ratio of distance upto which pushing is observed to the actual height of the casting) is found to decrease with increasing cooling rate (i.e. with decreasing casting height to chill thickness ratio or $H_{\text{cast}}/T_{\text{chill}}$) as shown in Fig. 2a. Fig.2b shows that the size of the clusters (formed during the pushing by the primary dendrites) decreases with increasing cooling rate (i.e. lower ratio).

In the case of ACI casting, macrosegregation of dispersoids leading to an inverted 'V' type particle free zone is observed in the bottom half of the casting as shown in Fig.1b. Presence of particle free zone is the result of multidirectional solidification. Also, the matrix macrostructure reveals the presence of equiaxed grains.

The microsegregation of particles has been studied in detail. Engulfment of particles by the secondary dendrite arm has also been observed in the top part of the castings as shown in Fig.3.

Figure 2. Variation of (a) normalised distance upto which pushing has occurred and (b) SiC_p cluster size with the ratio of the height of the casting to the chill thickness (H_{cast}/T_{chill}).

Based on the secondary DAS measurements, the local interface velocity (i.e the growth of the secondary dendrite arms) was calculated using the following relations applicable for the respective matrix alloys :

$$DAS = 7.5t_f^{0.39} \text{ -- for AC [11]} \quad (1)$$

$$DAS = 102.3X^{-0.33} \text{ -- for ACM [12]} \quad (2)$$

$$i.e. DAS = 20.3t_f^{0.33} \text{ -- for ACM} \quad (3)$$

(rewriting equation 2 in terms of solidification time)

$$V_i = \frac{DAS}{2t_f} \quad (4)$$

where DAS is the secondary dendrite arm spacing in μm , t_f is the local solidification time in seconds, V_i is the local interface velocity in $\mu m/s$ and X is the cooling rate in $^{\circ}C/s$.

Figure 3. Engulfment of SiC particle by secondary dendrite arm in AC4 in the top region of the casting.

The values of the V_i thus obtained, were compared with the velocities predicted by different theoretical models to check the validity of the models for the pushing/engulfment transition by a growing secondary dendrite arm in the last freezing region. This comparison is summarized in the Table 2. In both AC and ACM castings, predictions of UCJ, Cisse-Bolling and Sasikumar's models are in agreement with the experimental findings. However, Stefanescu's

Table 2. Results of the Experiments with Copper Chill at the Bottom ; Varying G & V

Casting & Particle Size (μm)	Local Interface Velocity ($\mu\text{m}/\text{sec.}$) & Experimental Observation	U.C.J. $V_{critical}$ ($\mu\text{m}/\text{sec.}$) & Prediction	Cisse-Bolling $V_{critical}$ ($\mu\text{m}/\text{sec.}$) & Prediction	Stefanescu $V_{critical}$ ($\mu\text{m}/\text{sec.}$) & Prediction	Sasikumar $V_{critical}$ ($\mu\text{m}/\text{sec.}$) & Prediction
AC 25.5	0.35 Engulfed	0.0152 Engulfment	0.185 Engulfment	3.747×10^3 Pushing	0.207 Engulfment
AC 28.0	0.248 Engulfed	0.0013 Engulfment	0.14 Engulfment	3.488×10^3 Pushing	0.198 Engulfment
ACM 6.5	5.38 Engulfed	0.234 Engulfment	11.2 Engulfment	1.47×10^4 Pushing	0.377 Engulfment
ACM 16.5	4.39 Engulfed	0.0363 Engulfment	0.684 Engulfment	5.92×10^3 Pushing	0.25 Engulfment

Models based on thermophysical properties of materials, also were compared with the observations of the present study. Heat conductivity ratio, as described by Zubko *et al.*, is 0.3526 in the present case whereas, heat diffusivity ratio as described by Surappa *et al.* is 0.4436. According to both the model predictions the particles should be pushed by the growing solid-liquid interface. Hence, these two models fail to explain the experimental observation of particle engulfment by the secondary dendrite arms, in the present study.

Figure 4. Variation in the solidification front velocity as a function of distance from the mold bottom and comparison with the theoretical model predictions.

In the case of ACI, the macro interface velocity along the central axis was obtained dividing the measured temperature gradient by the cooling rate. The variation of this macro interface velocity with distance from the mold bottom is plotted in Fig.4. This variation is compared with critical velocity values computed from various theoretical models. Predictions based on Stefanescu's model appear to be close to that observed in the present study.

2. EFFECT OF PARTICLES ON INTERFACE MORPHOLOGY AND SOLUTE SEGREGATION

Fig.5 shows the microstructure of AC4 casting. It is observed that the particle free region in the bottom part of the casting is columnar dendritic (Fig.5a), whereas the particle containing top part exhibits either cellular-dendritic or equiaxed-dendritic morphology (Fig.5b). This

Figure 5. Microstructure of AC4 casting showing (a) columnar dendritic structure in the particle free region and (b) cellular-dendritic structure in the particle containing top region.

Figure 6. Variation in the grain size as a function of distance from the mold bottom in the permanent mold castings.

Figure 7. SEM of an engulfed SiC particle in the unidirectionally solidified (growth direction is marked by arrows in the micrographs) AC4 composite. (a) an engulfed SiC particle (b) Elemental Cu mapping.

In the case of ACI casting, equiaxed grains are observed throughout the casting. However, in the particle depleted region, the grain sizes are larger than that in the regions containing

particles. Grain size measurement in the unreinforced alloy and the composite was made along the central axis. In the case of composite, grain size is markedly higher (Fig.6). SEM and EDAX observations reveal the presence of a Cu-rich layer of average $4\mu\text{m}$ thickness just beneath the SiC particle. A typical SEM picture of an engulfed SiC particle is shown in Fig.7a. The Cu mapping for the same region is shown in Fig.7b.

DISCUSSIONS

In Al-Cu-SiC_p system, since $\sigma_{ps} - (\sigma_{pl} + \sigma_{sl}) > 0$, the advancing interface exerts a repulsive force on the particle ahead of it. Steady-state particle pushing requires a constant feeding of liquid metal into the gap between the particle and the interface and this fluid flow in the gap generates a viscous drag force on the particle. Moreover, the density of SiC is more than the Al-Cu alloy melt and hence a buoyancy force also acts on the particle dragging it towards the interface. When the net force on the particle is positive towards growth direction, pushing occurs and if it is negative towards growth direction particle is engulfed. Now as predicted by the models, the magnitude of these forces depend on the velocity of the solidification front and in turn determines the critical velocity for pushing to engulfment transition.

It is found that none of the theoretical models are able to predict all the experimental results. It must be noted that all these models are evolved for plane front solidification, the dendritic solidification in the present experiments might be one of the reasons for the failure of these models in the present study. As pointed out by Sekhar and Trivedi [8], the particle acts as a barrier to the solute diffusion field ahead of an advancing interface and this influences the solute concentration gradient ahead of the interface, leading to a change in the interface shape. The shape of interface decides the magnitude of the net force on the particle and hence the conditions for engulfment. Also the large difference in thermal conductivity of the particle and the melt affects the shape of solidification front and hence conditions for engulfment.

It is well documented through theories and experiments that as the particle size increases critical velocity for trapping decreases. Particles pushed by the solid-liquid interface begin to accumulate. As expected, with faster cooling, the cluster sizes are smaller as compared to those obtained on slower cooling. Also with relatively slower cooling i.e. lower the growth rate, larger the distance over which clusters are pushed.

In the casting ACI, faster cooling rate near the periphery compared to that along central axis leads to entrapment of the particles after pushing for a short distance. While along the central axis, slower cooling promotes particle pushing over a longer distance before entrapment.

When an advancing solid-liquid interface comes sufficiently close to a particle, the solute diffusion field interacts with the particle and solute build-up occurs in the gap between the interface and the particle. Hence, when the particle is trapped and the interface moves ahead, it leaves behind a band of excess solute around the particle. Also, the presence of particles is believed to reduce the concentration gradient ahead of the interface and hence promotes a transition from dendritic to cellular-dendritic morphology [11] in the particle containing regions of AC and ACM castings.

CONCLUSIONS

Directional solidification of Al-Cu-SiC_p and Al-Cu-Mg-SiC_p composites lead to extensive particle pushing to the top part of castings. Particle free region increases with decreasing cooling rate leading to macrosegregation. Comparison of macro and microsegregation results

with the theoretical model predictions reveal the inadequacy of the models. Presence of particles are found to influence the growth morphology from columnar-dendritic to cellular-dendritic or equiaxed-dendritic. Also particles are found to promote coarser grain structures in composite castings compared to the unreinforced alloy. Solute segregation around SiC particles is observed in Al-Cu alloy composites. This is due to the physical barrier imposed by the particle to the diffusing solute flux.

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